

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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Feeding the Open Science extension to EC2U Connect Centre

Digital platform

DELIVERABLE 7.5
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D7.5 – Feeding the Open Science extension to EC2U Connect Centre

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I. Introduction

In order to raise awareness about Open Science and support researchers in changing to a more open and collaborative way of doing research, WP7 created resources and tools for the use of the EC2U community.

The University of Pavia is developing in their WP4 a specific extension of the EC2U Connect Centre to create a resource platform devoted to store and promote Open Science practices and tools created in WP7. In this deliverable (D7.5) we have compiled all the resources which are included in this platform which are:

- Open science learning materials (five instructional videos, two podcasts and written materials)
- EC2U Open Science Community

The aim of the extension is to strengthen the competences related to Open Science. The goal is that the Open Science platform will stay on as a permanent part of the EC2U Alliance and its updating with the changing needs of the EC2U Alliance community will be assigned to the EC2U Open Science community. The launch of the EC2U Open Science Community was announced in Poitiers on 11th and 12th June 2024.

I. Content of the Open Science extension to the EC2U Connect Centre

The Open Science platform is available on the [online Toolkit for Researchers' Career Development](#). It contains the following materials:

A. Open Science learning materials

1. Masterclasses videos on Open Science

- Why is Open Science important?
 - Experts from each partner university of the EC2U Alliance share their views on why Open Science is important in their native languages.
- Open science for scientists and opening science for non-scientists
 - Postdoctoral researcher Smriti Mehta from the University of California, Berkeley talks about Open Science and shares some examples of projects she is involved in that support Open Science practices.
- Pre-registration: What does it actually bring us?
 - Senior Research Fellow Lydia Laninga-Wijnen from the INVEST Flagship at the University of Turku discusses benefits and challenges related to pre-registration. She also shares some insights on how to write pre-registrations and what tools can be used.
- Baby steps for reproducible workflow in R – part 1: introduction
 - Senior researcher Juuso Repo from the INVEST Flagship at the University of Turku gives an introduction to reproducibility and why we need it. He also presents the steps for reproducible workflow in R.
- Baby steps for reproducible workflow in R – part 2: demo
 - Showing in action the steps introduced in the 'Baby steps for reproducible workflow in R - part 1: introduction', Senior researcher Juuso Repo presents a hands-on demo on reproducible workflow in RStudio.

Information on the Masterclasses videos on Open Science are described in more detail in D7.4: Masterclasses on Open Science. All videos are accessible online on the official EC2U YouTube channel and they can also be found on the EC2U Alliance website. Videos available in the [EC2U YouTube Channel Playlist](#).

2. Masterclasses podcasts on Open Science

- How does open workflows increase impact and enhance Open science?
 - In this episode Laura Niemi and Outi Nurmela from the University of Turku interview associate professor Caspar van Lissa from Tillburg University. The episode focuses on open workflows in research.
 - [Link to the podcast](#) on Soundcloud.
- How to make science more tangible for a broader audience?
 - In this episode Laura Niemi and Outi Nurmela from the University of Turku interview researcher Ties Fakkkel from the Erasmus University Rotterdam. The episode focuses on how researchers can make their research more tangible and accessible for a broader audience.
 - [Link to the podcast](#) on Soundcloud

Information on the Masterclasses podcasts on Open Science are described in more detail in D7.4: Masterclasses on Open Science. Podcasts are accessible via the EC2U Alliance website, and they can also be found directly on Soundcloud and [Spotify](#).

3. Written materials

- Open Science Survey results
 - The analysis of the case descriptions revealed that several novel and emerging Open Science practices are not yet widely established (D7.2). The analysis was based on the case descriptions about Open Science practices being implemented at the universities of the EC2U Alliance. (D7.1).
- Open science interviews
 - Six interviews with Open Science Champions, researchers who routinely implement Open Science practices in their own academic work and also promote Open Science in their own respective institutions (D7.3).
- Open Science Guidebook
 - A general-level and non-commercial practical online guide for researchers looking for information and tips on how to approach a range of Open Science practices (D7.3).

More detailed information on the written materials can be found in deliverables 7.1: Case descriptions on Open Science, 7.2: Open Science practices: Case synthesis and 7.3: Open Science Guidebook. The Open Science Guidebook is also accessible via [Zenodo](#).

B. EC2U Open Science Community

The EC2U Open Science Community is an international hub where academics interact and learn from their peers on how to apply Open Science practices and make their workflows more open. The promotion of Open Science and research is a collaborative effort and therefore the community invites all people interested in opening their research to embrace Open Science principles, policies and practices. The community supports members by offering peer to peer support, open educational materials and organising social events. The community also provides possibilities for opening up collaborations between academics and societal stakeholders to meet, inspire, and co-create.

The launch of the EC2U Open Science Community was announced at the "Kick-off the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem – Unveiling the University of the Future" event in Poitiers on 11th & 12th June 2024. The first event of the EC2U Open Science Community will be the community's online kick-off event on 26th September, 2024.

EC2U Open Science Community kick-off event

Time: 26.09.2024 at 10-11 CET

Location: Zoom (link shared to registered members)

Programme:

10.00-10.10 Introducing the aims of the EC2U Open Science Community (Dr. Laura Niemi, University of Turku)

10.10-10.30 What is Open Science and why it is important? (Dr. Lydia Laninga-Wijnen, University of Turku)

10.30-10.45 Good practices from the Open Science Community Turku (Dr. Lydia Laninga-Wijnen, University of Turku)

10.45-11.00 Selection of the community coordinator

After the kick-off event the EC2U Open Science Community will continue working based on the activities of the members of the community. The aim is for them to continue creating new open learning materials on Open Science to be fed to the Open Science extension of the EC2U Connect Centre.

II. List of previous deliverables

D7.1 Case descriptions on Open Science. Available: <https://ec2u.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/709/2023/10/D7.1-Case-descriptions.pdf>

D7.2 Open Science practices: Case synthesis. Available: <https://ec2u.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/709/2023/05/D7.2-Case-synthesis1.pdf>

D7.3 Open Science Guidebook. Available: <https://ec2u.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/709/2023/05/D7.3-Guidebook-for-Open-Science-champions1.pdf>

D7.4 Masterclasses on Open Science. Available: <https://ec2u.eu/ri4c2/work-package-7-open-ec2u/>

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